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The BonaRes Metadata Schema

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Abstract	<p>The BonaRes metadata schema provides a description for each metadata element available in the schema. Each element contains information such as its unique ID, a clear definition, an obligation and multiplicity statement as well as the data type and its data domain. The metadata schema combines international recognized standards for the description of geospatial data (INSPIRE Directive) and research data (DataCite 4.0). The compliance with DataCite 4.0 permits the assignment of a Digital Object Identifier to the research data. The Digital Object Identifier assures reliable and unambiguous access; supports re-use of the data and allows proper attribution and credit.</p>
Key words	BonaRes, Metadata, INSPIRE, DataCite, Open Data

Content

Definitions	1
Introduction.....	2
General requirements	2
DOI Creation	3
BonaRes Metadata Properties	4
Description	4
Categorization	12
Access	13
Distribution.....	16
Quality	18
Metadata	19
Data Model.....	21
Appendices	22
Appendix 1: Controlled List Definitions for <i>Date Types</i>	22
Appendix 2: Description of all available <i>Date types</i>	23
Appendix 3: Description of all available <i>Role types</i>	24
Appendix 4: Description of all available <i>Related Identifier Types</i>	27
Appendix 5: Description of all available <i>Relation Types</i>	28
Appendix 6: Description of all available <i>Resource types</i>	29
Appendix 7: Description of all available <i>Access constraints</i>	29
Appendix 8: Description of regularly used <i>Creative Commons</i> licenses	30
BonaRes Series	31

Definitions

Data owner: Person or institution with ownership rights to data and metadata. The data owner is not necessarily the data provider but can select the data provider as his/her deputy.

Data provider: Person in charge of providing data and metadata to the BonaRes Data Centre. Ideally, the data provider is assigned deputy for the data owner or his institution. The data provider is the most important point of contact for the BonaRes Data Centre.

Data user: Person using research data stored in and provided by the BonaRes Data Centre.

Embargo: Blocking period for the publication of data by the Data Centre on request by the data owner.

Lineage: a statement on process history and/or overall quality of the data. Where appropriate it may include a statement whether the data have been validated or quality assured, whether it is the official version (if multiple versions exist), and whether it has legal validity.

Metadata: Metadata are 'data about data' and contain information on who created the data how, necessary background information to the data, where they are located, characteristics of the file structure, intellectual property right (IPR) information etc. This descriptive information enables users to judge the usability of the data for their own purposes.

Set of data (dataset): At a minimum, the combination of data and associated metadata.

Introduction

This document describes the BonaRes metadata schema for soil research data developed as part of the BonaRes project. General requirements of the metadata are discussed in the overview chapter, which is followed by a description of prerequisites for a DOI registration. The last chapter contains a detailed listing of all BonaRes metadata element within the schema.

Metadata provide the explanatory information necessary to understand and re-use research data. Therefore, metadata enable data to be interpreted correctly. How well the data are described with metadata will largely determine how discoverable and thus re-usable they remain over time.

An essential task of the BonaRes Data Centre is the secure storage of research data and the assurance of their long term discoverability and accessibility. The following section provides all necessary metadata elements needed to accurately describe the data produced. This descriptive metadata schema combines international recognized standards for the description of geospatial data (INSPIRE¹ Directive) and research data (DataCite 4.0²). The compliance with DataCite 4.0 permits the assignment of a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to the research data. The DOI assures reliable and unambiguous access; supports re-use of the data and allow proper attribution and credit.

In order to secure reproducibility and re-usability of research data, it is necessary to obtain accurate information on the attributes or attribute values occurring in the dataset. The BonaRes metadata schema provides such metadata elements to describe existing attributes.

Column
Value
Value

General requirements

It is of great interest for researchers and data providers to increase the visibility of research data and to facilitate its allocation and citation. Therefore, data providers are strongly encouraged to submit all sets of metadata properties and their sub-properties. The here presented BonaRes metadata schema provides two different levels of obligation for the metadata properties. Elements within a mandatory field must be provided while elements within an optional field should be provided if available.

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
1	Title	This is a mandatory field.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
2	Temporal extent	This field is optional (e.g. from 2008-01-01 to 2008-12-31).	Optional	[0..n]	Date (ISO 8601)

The multiplicity column indicates the quantity constraints for the metadata elements (not repeatable vs. repeatable). A typical example for a not repeatable [1] mandatory element is publication year³ since the data can only be published once. As an example of a repeatable mandatory [1..n] element, is the funding reference⁴ mentioned here. The funding reference element can be filled repeatedly

¹ <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>

² <https://schema.datacite.org/meta/kernel-4.0/index.html> DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5438/0013>

³ The year when the data was or will be made publicly available.

⁴ Information about financial support for the resource being registered.

with details about several (one or many) funding bodies which supported the creation of the registered resource.

The column data type & domain indicates value constraints. Controlled list values will be implemented as drop-down menu. Example values are provided at the end of the definition column and illustrate the description of the metadata element by providing a concrete case.

	Not Repeatable	Repeatable
Yes	[1]	[1..n]
No	[0..1]	[0..n]

For certain data types, the BonaRes data centre may extract metadata elements and pre-fill the metadata editor with the fetched information. A typical example would be the extraction of the feature bounding box as well as the count of the number of features from an ESRI shapefile. Metadata elements which can be fetched and automatically pre-filled are marked with the BonaRes logo (🌐) located in the ID column of each metadata table. In order to increase the international visibility and reuse of the research data, the English language was defined as a standard language for the metadata description.

DOI Creation

On request, The BonaRes Data Centre will render a DOI using the following six mandatory metadata properties: **Creator¹ (Date of Publication²): Title³. Publisher⁴. Resource Type⁵. Identifier⁶** which may translate into the following Citation

- Mustermann, Max¹ (2017²): Local Non-Gridded Surfaces of Selected Soil Characteristics³. BonaRes Datenzentrum (ZALF)⁴. Dataset⁵. <http://bonares.de/10.20387/726855>⁶

Please note: From the list of contact type (ID xxx) the property creator is the only element which will be used to formulate the citation (name allocation), please consider the prominence of the role.

BonaRes Metadata Properties

Description

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
1	Title	A characteristic, unique name by which the dataset is known.	Mandatory	[1] ³	Character String (Free text)
1.1	@Title (german)	German translation of the Title.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
2	Alternate title	A short name by which the dataset is also known. (e.g. <u>DCW</u> for " <u>digital chart of the world</u> ").	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
2.1	@Title type	The type of Alternate title. If short title is used, title type is mandatory (e.g. <u>alternative title</u>).	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • alternative title • subtitle • translated title • other
3	Summary	Brief narrative summary of the content of the dataset.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
3.1	@Summary (german)	German translation of the Summary.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
4	Graphic overview	Graphic that provides an illustration of the dataset.	Optional	[0..n]	Image (.png, .tif, .jpg)
5	Date	The date when the dataset was or will be made <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • publicly available • last revised • created • submitted • etc. <p>(e.g. <u>01/01/2010</u>)</p>	Mandatory	[4..n]	Date (ISO 8601)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multi- plicity	Data type & Do- main
5.1	@Date type	The type of Date. (e.g. <u>Created</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accepted • Available [1]² • Collected • Copyrighted • Created [1] • Issued [1] • Submitted • Updated [1] • Valid <p>See Appendix 1 and Appendix 2 for definitions.</p>
6	Responsible party	The main researchers involved in producing (collecting, managing, distributing, or otherwise contributing to the development of the dataset) the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order. Will be cited if <i>Author</i> is used as contact type.	Mandatory	[1..n]	
6.1	@Name	The name of the person. The personal name format should be: family, given. (e.g. <u>Miller, Elizabeth</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
6.2	@Organisation	The name of the organisation. (e.g. <u>Technische Universität Berlin</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.3	@Position	The position the person is currently holding. (e.g. <u>research associate</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multi- plicity	Data type & Do- main
6.4	@Role	The role of the person to the submitted dataset. (e.g. <u>author</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Collector • Data Curator • Editor • Hosting Institution 🌐 • Other • Producer • Project Leader [1] • Project Manager • Project Member • Registration Agency 🌐 • Registration Authority 🌐 • Related Person • Research Group • Researcher • Rights Holder • Sponsor • Supervisor • Work Package Leader • Author [1] ¹ • Custodian • Distributor • Originator • Owner • Point of Contact • Principal Investigator • Processor • Publisher ⁴ 🌐 • Resource Provider • User See Appendix 3 for definitions.

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
6.5	@Name identifier	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes. (e.g. <u>0000-0001-5000-0007</u>)	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
6.6	@Name identifier schema	The name of the name identifier schema. If <code>Name identifier</code> is used, <code>Name identifier schema</code> is mandatory. (e.g. <u>ORCID</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
6.7	@Identifier schema URI	The URI of the name identifier schema. (e.g. <u>http://orcid.org</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (URI)
6.8	@Phone	The current office phone number.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.9	@Facsimile	The current office fax number.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.10	@Delivery point	The office address.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.11	@City	The city the office is placed in.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.12	@Administrative area	The province the city is in. (e.g. <u>Berlin</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.13	@ZIP	The official postal code of the city.	Optional	[0..1]	Integer / Numerical
6.14	@Country	The country name.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
6.15	@E-mail address	The Email address of the person.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
7	Funding reference	Information about financial support (funding) for the dataset being registered.	Mandatory	[1..n]	
7.1	@Funder name	Name of the funding provider. (e.g. <u>European Commission</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
7.2	@Identifier	Uniquely identifies a funding entity, according to various types. (e.g. <u>http://doi.org/10.13039/501100000780</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	URI
7.3	@Identifier type	The type of the <code>Identifier</code> . (e.g. <u>BMBF</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DFG • BMBF • PTJ • DAAD • Other

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
7.4	@Award number	The code assigned by the funder to a sponsored award (grant). (e.g. <u>282625</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
7.5	@URI	The URI leading to a page provided by the funder for more information about the award (grant). (e.g. <u>http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/100180_en.html</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	URI
7.6	@Award title	The human readable title of the award (grant). (e.g. <u>MOTivational strength of ecosystem services</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
8	Coordinate Reference system	Description of the coordinate reference system(s) used in the dataset. (e.g. <u>ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETRS89 / UTM zone 32N or 33N • Gauss-Krueger (zone 2, 3, 4 or 5) • ETRS 89 (lat/lon) • WGS 84 (lat/lon) • etc.
9	Geographic bounding box	The spatial limits of a box. A box is defined by two geographic points. Lower left corner and upper right corner. Each point is defined by its longitude and latitude value.	Mandatory	[1..n]	
9.1	@North latitude	Northern latitudinal dimension of the Geographic bounding box.	Mandatory	[1]	Decimal / Numerical
9.2	@South latitude	Southern latitudinal dimension of the Geographic bounding box.	Mandatory	[1]	Decimal / Numerical
9.3	@West longitude	Western longitudinal dimension of the Geographic bounding box.	Mandatory	[1]	Decimal / Numerical
9.4	@East longitude	Eastern longitudinal dimension of the Geographic bounding box.	Mandatory	[1]	Decimal / Numerical
10	Geographic identifier	Spatial reference in the form of a label or code that identifies a location.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
11	Temporal extent	The time period in which the resource content was collected (e.g. <u>From 2008-01-01 to 2008-12-31</u>)	Optional	[0..n]	Date (ISO 8601)
12	Spatial representation type	Method used to spatially represent geographic information.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • grid • stereoModel • textTable • tin • vector • video
13	Language	Language used within the dataset. (e.g. <u>eng</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Codelist based on ISO 639-2
14	Character set	The character encoding used in the dataset. (e.g. <u>utf-8</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Controlled List Value)
15	Identifier (DOI)	The <i>Identifier</i> is a unique string that identifies a resource. Will be assigned by the BonaRes Data Centre. (<u>http://bonares.de/10.20387/72685</u>)	Mandatory	[1] ⁶	Character String (Free text)
16	Related identifier	Identifiers of related resources. These must be globally unique identifiers.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
16.1	@Identifier	The <i>Identifier</i> of related resources. This must be a globally unique identifier.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
16.2	@Identifier type	The type of the Related identifier. If Related identifier is used Identifier type is mandatory. (e.g. bibcode)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Values): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARK • DOI • EAN13 • EISSN • Handle • IGSN • ISBN • ISSN • ISTC • LISSN • LSID • PMID • PURL • UPC • URL • URN • arXiv • bibcode

See [Appendix 4](#) for definitions.

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multi- plicity	Data type & Do- main
16.3	@Relation type	<p>Description of the relationship of the resource being registered (A) and the related resource (B).</p> <p>If <code>Related identifier</code> is used <code>Relation type</code> is mandatory.</p>	Mandatory	[1]	<p>Character String (Controlled List Values):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cites • Compiles • Continues • Documents • HasMetadata • HasPart • IsCitedBy • IsCompiledBy • IsContinuedBy • IsDerivedFrom • IsDocument- edBy • IsIdenticalTo • IsMetadataFor • IsNewVersion- Of • IsOriginal- FormOf • IsPartOf • IsPreviousVer- sionOf • IsReferencedBy • IsReviewedBy • IsSourceOf • IsSupple- mentTo • IsSupplement- edBy • IsVariant- FormOf • References • Reviews <p>See Appendix 5 for definitions.</p>
17	Supplemental Information	<p>Supplemental information material such as field notes, images or code, can be uploaded with your dataset. Submitted supplementary items are made available exactly as they are received. Please submit a collection of supplemental material within a .zip file.</p>	Optional	[0..1]	Compressed file (.zip)

Categorization

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
18	Resource type 	A description of the resource. (e.g. <u>dataset</u>)	Mandatory	[1] ⁵	Character String (Fixed List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dataset • nonGeographic Dataset • Service <p>See Appendix 6 for details.</p>
19	Categories	Name of the hierarchy levels for which the metadata is provided. (e.g. <u>SIGNAL</u>)	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inplamint • DiControl • SIGNAL • SUSALPS • SOILAssist • I4S • Soil³ • ORDIAmur • InnoSoilPhos • CATCHY • BonaRes Center • LTFE • Other
20	Keywords	The keyword value is a commonly used word, formalised word or phrase used to describe the subject. (e.g. <u>water salination</u>). Supported by AGROVOC and GEMET thesauri.	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Free text)
20.1	@Keyword type	Please choose the type of the keyword.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discipline • Place • Stratum • Temporal • Theme

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
20.2	@Thesaurus	Select the name of the formally registered Thesaurus. (e.g. <u>GE-MET</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GEMET • AGROVOC
20.3	@Date	The <code>Date</code> when the thesaurus was either created, published or revised.	Mandatory	[1]	Date (ISO 8601)
20.4	@Date type	The type of date. (e.g. <u>Created</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation • Publication • Revision
21	Topic category	The general theme of the dataset. (e.g. <u>agriculture</u>)	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biota • Environment • Farming • Location • etc.

Access

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
22	Geodata link <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ressource Type • Path • Version 	The <code>Geodata link</code> shall provide the data download information. (The information will be provided by the BonaRes Data Centre).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multi- plicity	Data type & Do- main
23	Use limitations	<p>Restrictions applied to assure the protection of privacy or intellectual property, and any special restrictions or limitations or warnings on using the resource or metadata. (e.g. <u>Re-ports, articles, papers, scientific and non-scientific works of any form, including tables, maps, or any other kind of output, in printed or elec-tronic form, based in whole or in part on the data supplied, must contain an acknowledgement of the form: "Data re-used from the BonaRes Data Centre www.bonares.de. The Name of the data data were created as part of BonaRes Module A-Project research activities."</u> Although every care has been taken in preparing and testing the data, BonaRes Module A-Project and BonaRes Data Centre cannot guarantee that the data are correct; neither does BonaRes Module A-Project and BonaRes Data Centre accept any liability whatsoever for any error, missing data or omission in the data, or for any loss or dam-age arising from its use. The BonaRes Module A-Project and BonaRes Data Centre will not be responsible for any direct or indirect use which might be made of the data. The access to this data is re-stricted during embargo time. If prior access is requested, contact the data owner/author.)</p>	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
24	Access constraints	This metadata element shall provide information on the <code>Access constraints</code> applied to assure the protection of privacy or intellectual property, and any special restrictions or limitations on obtaining the resource. (e.g. Licence)	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WSS protected • Copyright • Intellectual property rights • License • Other restrictions • Patent • Patent pending • Restricted • Trademark See Appendix 7 for details.
25	Use constraints	This metadata element shall provide information on the <code>Use constraints</code> applied to assure the protection of privacy or intellectual property (e.g. Trademark)	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please see <code>Access constraints</code> (ID 24).
26	Other constraints	Any rights information for this resource. (e.g. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Germany License).	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CC 0 • CC BY • CC BY-SA • CC BY-NC • CC BY-ND • CC BY-NC-SA • CC BY-NC-ND See Appendix 8 for details.

Distribution

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
27	Online resource 	The Resource Locator is the 'navigation section' of a metadata record which point users to the location (URL) where the data can be downloaded, or to where additional information about the resource may be provided. (The information will be provided by the BonaRes Data Centre)			
27.1	@URL	A web address where the resource can be found.	Mandatory	[1..n]	URL
27.2	@Function	Describes the format or content behind the URL link.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Download • Information • Offline Access • Order • Search
28	Format	Technical Format of the resource.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
28.1	@Format name	Use file extension or MIME type where possible. (e.g. <u>PDF</u> , <u>XML</u>)	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
28.2	@Format version	The version number of the resource. Suggested practice: track major_version.minor_version. (e.g. <u>3.1</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29	Responsible party	Please see Responsible party (ID 6).	Mandatory	[1..n]	
29.1	@Name	Please see @Name (ID 6.1).	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
29.2	@Organisation	Please see @Organisation (ID 6.2).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.3	@Position	Please see @Position (ID 6.3).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
29.4	@Role	The role of the person to the submitted dataset. (e.g. <u>distributor</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distributor • Resource Provider <p>See Appendix 3 for definitions.</p>
29.5	@Name identifier	Please see @Name identifier (ID 6.5).	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
29.6	@Name identifier schema	Please see @Name identifier schema (ID 6.6).	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
29.7	@Identifier schema URI	Please see @Identifier schema URI (ID 6.7).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (URI)
29.8	@Phone	Please see @Phone (ID 6.8).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.9	@Facsimile	Please see @Facsimile (ID 6.9).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.1 0	@Delivery point	Please see @Delivery point (ID 6.10).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.1 1	@City	Please see @City (ID 6.11).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.1 2	@Administrative area	Please see @Administrative area (ID 6.12).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.1 3	@ZIP	Please see @ZIP (ID 6.13).	Optional	[0..1]	Integer / Numerical
29.1 4	@Country	Please see @Country (ID 6.14).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
29.1 5	@E-mail address	Please see @E-mail address (ID 6.15).	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

Quality

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
30	Equivalent scale	The level of detail of the dataset expressed as scale denominator. Mandatory if an <code>Equivalent scale</code> can be specified. (e.g. <u>50000</u> if 1:50000 map scale)	Optional	[0..n]	Positive Integer / Numerical
31	Distance	The level of detail of the dataset expressed as ground sampling distance. Mandatory if a resolution distance can be specified. (e.g. <u>0.25</u> (degrees))	Optional	[0..1]	Decimal / Numerical
31.1	@Unit	A unit of measure of the distance value.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centimeter • Decimeter • Kilometer • Meter
32	Lineage statement	General explanation of the data producer's knowledge about the lineage of a dataset.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
33	Conformity result	Information regarding the conformance of to BonaRes Metadata Schema. The metadata shall include information on the degree of conformity.	Mandatory	[1]	
33.1	@Passed	This is the degree of conformity of the dataset to the implementing rules the BonaRes Schema.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • true (passed) • false (did not pass) • unknown (not evaluated)
33.2	@Specification	Citation of the product specification or user requirement against which data is being evaluated. (e.g. <u>BonaRes Metadata Schema 1.0, August 2017</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
33.3	@Date	An effective date.	Mandatory	[1]	Date (ISO 8601)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
33.4	@Date type	The type of date.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation • Publication • Revision
33.5	@Explanation	Give an Explanation about the conformity check. (e.g. <u>See the referenced specification.</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

Metadata

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
34	Metadata identifier 🗄️	The unique identifier for this metadata set.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
35	Parent identifier	A file identifier of the metadata to which this metadata is a subset (child). (e.g. <u>73c0f49f-1502-48ee-b038-052563f36527</u>)	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
36	Date stamp	The date when the metadata were created. (e.g. <u>28/08/2017</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Date (ISO 8601)
37	Responsible party	The person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise field issues related to the resource.	Mandatory	[1..n]	
37.1	@Name	The name of the creator/contact person. The personal name format should be: family, given. (e.g. <u>Miller, Elizabeth</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
37.2	@Organisation	The name of the organisation. (e.g. <u>Technische Universität Berlin</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.3	@Position	The position the person is currently holding. (e.g. <u>research associate</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.4	@Role	The role of the person to the submitted dataset. (e.g. <u>Point of Contact</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled List Value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Point of Contact

See [Appendix 3](#) for definitions.

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
37.5	@Name identifier	Uniquely identifies an individual or legal entity, according to various schemes. (e.g. <u>0000-0001-5000-0007</u>)	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
37.6	@Name identifier schema	The name of the name identifier scheme. If name identifier is used, name identifier schema is mandatory. (e.g. <u>ORCID</u>)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
37.7	@Identifier schema URI	The URI of the name identifier schema. (e.g. <u>http://orcid.org</u>)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (URI)
37.8	@Phone	The current office phone number.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.9	@Facsimile	The current office fax number.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.10	@Delivery point	The office address.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.11	@City	The city the office is placed in.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.12	@Administrative area	The province the city is in. (e.g. Berlin)	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.13	@ZIP	The official postal code of the city.	Optional	[0..1]	Integer / Numerical
37.14	@Country	The country name.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
37.15	@E-mail address	The Email address of the person.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
38	Character set	The character encoding used in the dataset. (e.g. UTF-8)	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
39	Language	Language used for documenting the metadata. (e.g. English)	Mandatory	[1]	Codelist based on ISO 639-2
40	Metadata standard name	The name of the metadata standard (including profile name) used.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
41	Metadata standard version	Version (profile) of the metadata standard used.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)

Data Model

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multiplicity	Data type & Domain
42	Thumbnail	Upload a graphical representation of an entity-relationship diagram between the provided data resources.	Optional	[0..1]	Image (.png, .tif)
43	Attributes	Description of the attribute values occurring in the dataset.	Mandatory	[1..n]	
43.1	@Name	Name of the column (expected for each column).	Mandatory	[1..n]	Character String (Free text)
43.2	@Long name	Column name without abbreviations	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
43.3	@Description	Detailed <i>Description</i> of the column data.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
43.4	@Unit	Unit of the data; Ideally SI-Unit.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
43.5	@Methods	If standard <i>Methods</i> were applied, the standard used should be specified here. Provide information about used instruments.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
43.6	@Quality	If measures are taken to check the <i>Quality</i> of the data, please specify.	Optional	[0..1]	Character String (Free text)
43.7	@Data type	A classification of data which tells how to use the data. The type defines the operations that can be done on the data, the meaning of the data, and the way values of that type can be stored.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Controlled list value): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Text • Date • Time • Numerical • Boolean
43.8	@Domain	Refers to all the values which a data element may contain.	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)
43.9	@Missing value	Codes for missing values, "no specification". (e.g. <NA>, <missing>).	Mandatory	[1]	Character String (Free text)

ID	Element	Definition	Obligation	Multi- plicity	Data type & Domain
43.1 0	@Foreign key	Table relationships contain Primary Key and Foreign key constraints. A Foreign key is a key used to link two tables together. A Foreign key in a table points to a Primary Key in another table.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
43.1 0.1	Identifier	A file Identifier of the metadata to which this metadata is a subset (child). (e.g. 73c0f49f-1502-48ee-b038-052563f36527)	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
43.1 0.2	Table	The Table name to which this table is relating to.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)
43.1 0.3	Column	The Column name of the foreign key.	Optional	[0..n]	Character String (Free text)

Appendices

Appendix 1: Controlled List Definitions for *Date Types*

Figure 1: Timeline for preparing and publishing a dataset.

Appendix 2: Description of all available *Date types*

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Accepted	The date that the publisher accepted the resource into their system.	To indicate the start of an embargo period, use "Submitted".
Available [1]	The date the resource was or will be made publicly available.	To indicate the end of an embargo period, use Available (default 24 month).
Collected	The date or date range in which the dataset content was collected.	To indicate precise or particular timeframes in which research was conducted.
Copyrighted	The specific, documented date at which the dataset receives a copyrighted status, if applicable.	
Created [1]	The date the dataset itself was put together; a single date for a final component, e.g., the finalised file with all of the data.	Recommended for discovery.
Issued [1]	The date that the dataset is published or distributed to the data centre.	
Submitted	The date the author submits the resource to the publisher. This could be different from "Accepted" if the publisher then applies a selection process.	Recommended for discovery. To indicate the start of an embargo period, use Submitted.
Updated [1]	The date of the last update (last revision) to the dataset, when the dataset is being added to.	
Valid	The date or date range during which the dataset or resource is accurate.	

Appendix 3: Description of all available *Role types*

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Data Collector	Person/institution responsible for finding, gathering/collecting data under the guidelines of the author(s) or Principal Investigator (PI).	May also use when crediting survey conductors, interviewers, event or condition observers, person responsible for monitoring key instrument data.
Data Curator	Person tasked with reviewing, enhancing, cleaning, or standardizing metadata and the associated data submitted for storage, use, and maintenance within a data centre or repository.	While the “Data Manager” is concerned with digital maintenance, the Data Curator’s role encompasses quality assurance focused on content and metadata. This includes checking whether the submitted dataset is complete, with all files and components as described by submitter, whether the metadata is standardized to appropriate systems and schema, whether specialized metadata is needed to add value and ensure access across disciplines, and determining how the metadata might map to search engines, database products, and automated feeds.
Editor	A person who oversees the details related to the publication format of the resource.	Note: if the Editor is to be credited in place of multiple creators, the Editor’s name may be supplied as Creator, with “(Ed.)” appended to the name.
Hosting Institution	Typically, the organisation allowing the resource to be available on the internet through the provision of its hardware/software/operating support.	May also be used for an organisation that stores the data offline. Often a data centre (if that data centre is not the “publisher” of the resource.)
Other	Any person or institution making a significant contribution to the development and/or maintenance of the resource, but whose contribution does not “fit” other controlled vocabulary for Type.	Could be a photographer, artist, or writer whose contribution helped to publicize the resource (as opposed to creating it), a reviewer of the resource, someone providing administrative services to the author (such as depositing updates into an online repository, analysing usage, etc.), or one of many other roles.
Producer	Typically a person or organisation responsible for the artistry and form of a media product.	In the data industry, this may be a company “producing” DVDs that package data for future dissemination by a distributor.

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Project Leader [1]	Person officially designated as head of project team or subproject team instrumental in the work necessary to development of the resource.	The Project Leader is not “re-removed” from the work that resulted in the resource; he or she remains intimately involved throughout the life of the particular project team.
Project Manager	Person officially designated as manager of a project. Project may consist of one or many project teams and sub-teams.	The manager of a project normally has more administrative responsibility than actual work involvement.
Project Member	Person on the membership list of a designated project/project team.	This vocabulary may or may not indicate the quality, quantity, or substance of the person’s involvement.
Registration Agency	Institution/organisation officially appointed by a Registration Authority to handle specific tasks within a defined area of responsibility.	DataCite is a Registration Agency for the International DOI Foundation (IDF). One of DataCite’s tasks is to assign DOI prefixes to the allocating agents who then assign the full, specific character string to data clients, provide metadata back to the DataCite registry, etc.
Registration Authority	A standards-setting body from which Registration Agencies obtain official recognition and guidance.	The IDF serves as the Registration Authority for the International Standards Organisation (ISO) in the area/domain of Digital Object Identifiers.
Related Person	A person without a specifically defined role in the development of the resource, but who is someone the author wishes to recognize.	This person could be an author’s intellectual mentor, a person providing intellectual leadership in the discipline or subject domain, etc.
Research Group	Typically refers to a group of individuals with a lab, department, or division; the group has a particular, defined focus of activity.	May operate at a narrower level of scope; may or may not hold less administrative responsibility than a project team.
Researcher	A person involved in analysing data or the results of an experiment or formal study. May indicate an intern or assistant to one of the authors who helped with research but who was not so “key” as to be listed as an author.	Should be a person, not an institution. Note that a person involved in the gathering of data would fall under the type “Data Collector.” The researcher may find additional data online and correlate it to the data collected for the experiment or study, for example.

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Rights Holder	Person or institution owning or managing property rights, including intellectual property rights over the resource.	
Sponsor	Person or organisation that issued a contract or under the auspices of which a work has been written, printed, published, developed, etc.	Includes organisations that provide in-kind support, through donation, provision of people or a facility or instrumentation necessary for the development of the resource, etc.
Supervisor	Designated administrator over one or more groups/teams working to produce a resource or over one or more steps of a development process.	
Work Package Leader	A Work Package is a recognized data product, not all of which is included in publication. The package, instead, may include notes, discarded documents, etc. The Work Package Leader is responsible for ensuring the comprehensive contents, versioning, and availability of the Work Package during the development of the resource.	
Author [1]	The main researchers involved in producing the data, or the authors of the publication, in priority order.	May be a corporate/institutional or personal name.
Custodian	Custodian	Custodian
Distributor	Institution tasked with responsibility to generate/disseminate copies of the resource in either electronic or print form.	Works stored in more than one archive/repository may credit each as a distributor.
Originator	Originator	Originator
Owner	Owner	Owner
Point of contact	Person with knowledge of how to access, troubleshoot, or otherwise field issues related to the resource.	May also be "Point of contact" in organisation that controls access to the resource, if that organisation is different from Publisher, Distributor, Data Manager.
Principal Investigator	Principal Investigator	Principal Investigator
Processor	Processor	Processor

Option	Description	Usage Notes
Publisher	The name of the entity that holds, archives, publishes prints, distributes, releases, issues, or produces the resource.	This property will be used to formulate the citation, so consider the prominence of the role.
Resource Provider	Resource Provider	Resource Provider

Appendix 4: Description of all available *Related Identifier Types*

Option	Description
ARK	Archival Resource Key; URL designed to support long-term access to information objects. In general, ARK syntax is of the form (brackets indicate [optional] elements: [http://NMA/]ark:/NAAN/Name[Qualifier])
DOI	Digital Object Identifier; a character string used to uniquely identify an object. A DOI name is divided into two parts, a prefix and a suffix, separated by a slash.
EAN13	European Article Number, now renamed International Article Number, but retaining the original acronym, is a 13-digit barcoding standard which is a superset of the original 12-digit Universal Product Code (UPC) system.
EISSN	Standard Serial Number; ISSN used to identify periodicals in electronic form (eISSN or e-ISSN).
Handle	A handle is an abstract reference to a resource.
IGSN	International Geo Sample Number; a 9-digit alphanumeric code that uniquely identifies samples from our natural environment and related sampling features.
ISBN	International Standard Book Number; a unique numeric book identifier. There are 2 formats: a 10-digit ISBN format and a 13-digit ISBN.
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number; a unique 8-digit number used to identify a print or electronic periodical publication.
ISTC	International Standard Text Code; a unique “number” assigned to a textual work. An ISTC consists of 16 numbers and/or letters.
LISSN	The linking ISSN or ISSN-L enables collocation or linking among different media versions of a continuing resource.
LSID	Life Science Identifiers; a unique identifier for data in the Life Science domain. Format: urn:lsid:authority:namespace:id identifier:revision
PMID	PubMed identifier; a unique number assigned to each PubMed record.
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator. A PURL has three parts: (1) a protocol, (2) a resolver address, and (3) a name.
UPC	Universal Product Code is a barcode symbology used for tracking trade items in stores. Its most common form, the UPC-A, consists of 12 numerical digits.

Option	Description
URL	Uniform Resource Locator, also known as web address, is a specific character string that constitutes a reference to a resource. The syntax is: <code>scheme://domain:port/path?query_string#fragment_id</code>
URN	Uniform Resource Name; is a unique and persistent identifier of an electronic document. The syntax is: <code>urn:<NID>:<NSS></code> The leading urn: sequence is case-insensitive, <NID> is the namespace identifier, <NSS> is the namespace-specific string.
arXiv	arXiv identifier; arXiv.org is a repository of preprints of scientific papers in the fields of mathematics, physics, astronomy, computer science, quantitative biology, statistics, and quantitative finance.
bibcode	Astrophysics Data System bibliographic codes; a standardized 19 character identifier according to the syntax <code>yyyyjjjjvvvmmppppa</code> . See http://info-uri.info/registry/OAIHandler?verb=GetRecord&metadataPrefix=reg&identifier=info:bibcode/

Appendix 5: Description of all available *Relation Types*

Option	Description
Is Cited By	indicates that B includes A in a citation
Cites	indicates that A includes B in a citation
Is Supplement To	indicates that A is a supplement to B
Is Supplemented By	indicates that B is a supplement to A
Is Continued By	indicates A is continued by the work B
Continues	indicates A is a continuation of the work B
Has Metadata	Indicates resource A has additional metadata B
Is Metadata For	Indicates additional metadata A for a resource B
Is New Version Of	indicates A is a new edition of B, where the new edition has been modified or updated
Is Previous Version Of	indicates A is a previous edition of B
Is Part Of	indicates A is a portion of B; may be used for elements of a series
Has Part	indicates A includes the part B
Is Referenced By	indicates A is used as a source of information by B
References	indicates B is used as a source of information for A
Is Documented By	indicates B is documentation about/ explaining A
Documents	indicates A is documentation about B
Is Compiled By	indicates B is used to compile or create A
Compiles	indicates B is the result of a compile or creation event using A

Option	Description
Is Variant Form Of	indicates A is a variant or different form of B, e.g. calculated or calibrated form or different packaging
Is Original Form Of	indicates A is the original form of B
Is Identical To	indicates that A is identical to B, for use when there is a need to register two separate instances of the same resource
Is Reviewed By	indicates that A is reviewed by B
Reviews	indicates that A is a review of B
Is Derived From	indicates B is a source upon which A is based
Is Source Of	indicates A is a source upon which B is based

Appendix 6: Description of all available *Resource types*

Option	Description	Link to Source
Dataset	Identifiable collection of data [ISO 19115]	INSPIRE glossary: dataset
Service	Means the operations which may be performed, by invoking a computer application, on the spatial data contained in spatial datasets or on the related metadata;	INSPIRE glossary: Spatial data services

Appendix 7: Description of all available *Access constraints*

Option	Description
Copyright	The exclusive right to the publication, production, or sale of the rights to a literary, dramatic, musical, or artistic work, or to the use of a commercial print or label, granted by law for a specified period of time to an author, composer, artist, distributor.
Intellectual Property Rights	The rights to financial benefit from and control of distribution of non-tangible property that is a result of creativity.
License	Formal permission to do something.
Other Restrictions	Limitation not listed.
Patent	Government has granted exclusive right to make, sell, use or license an invention or discovery.
Patent Pending	Produced or sold information awaiting a patent.
Restricted	Withheld from general circulation or disclosure.
Trademark	A name, symbol, or other device identifying a product, officially registered and legally restricted to the use of the owner or manufacturer

Appendix 8: Description of regularly used *Creative Commons* licenses⁵

Icon	Description	Acronym	Allows remix culture	Allows commercial use	Allows Free Cultural Works	Meets “Open Definition”
	Freeing content globally without restrictions	CC0	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Attribution alone	CC BY	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Attribution + ShareAlike	CC BY-SA	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Attribution + Noncommercial	CC BY-NC	Yes	No	No	No
	Attribution + NoDerivatives	CC BY-ND	No	Yes	No	No
	Attribution + Noncommercial + ShareAlike	CC BY-NC-SA	Yes	No	No	No
	Attribution + Noncommercial + NoDerivatives	CC BY-NC-ND	No	No	No	No

⁵ [Wikipedia - Creative Commons Licenses](#)

Previous publications

- 2017/2 Hoffmann et al. Overview of relevant standards for the BonaRes-Program.
DOI: 10.20387/BonaRes-FK84-PCR9
- 2017/1 Svoboda, N., Heinrich, U. The BonaRes Data Guideline.
DOI: 10.20387/BonaRes-E1AZ-ETD7

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BonaRes is short for “Soil as a Sustainable Resource for the Bioeconomy”. The focus lies on the sustainable use of soils as a limited resource. BonaRes extends the evidence base for scientists and decision-makers regarding the soil systems to improve the productivity of soils and other soil functions while developing new strategies for a sustainable management of soils.

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